

Effect of Different Molecular Structure on Resin based Solid Electrolyte for Structural Composite Battery

Jaehoon Choi ^{1*}, Bronwyn Fox ³, Salwan Al-Assafi ², Russell J. Varley ¹ and Minoo Naebe ¹

*Contact details : choija@deakin.edu.au

1. Carbon Nexus at the Institute for Frontier Materials (IFM), Deakin University, Waurn Ponds, VIC, 3216, Australia 2. Carbon Nexus, Institute for Frontier Materials (IFM), Deakin University, Waurn Ponds, VIC, 3216, Australia 3. Quickstep Holdings Limited Building LA, Deakin University, 75 Pigdons Road, Waurn Ponds, VIC, 3216, Australia 4. Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of Technology, Hawthorn, Victoria, 3122, Australia

Introduction

Evolution of Automotive Panel

Current Challenges and Target

Objective of the Study

- To investigate the ethylene oxide (EO) based SPE using different curing agents (linear, alicyclic and aromatic) to create the different molecular structure matrixes
- To confirm whether the trade-off relationship between mechanical and electrochemical properties can be enhanced

Experimental

Scheme of Solid Polyelectrolyte

Coin Cell Fabrication

Characterisation Techniques

Thermal Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermal stability by TGA • Glass transition temperature (T_g) by DSC
Mechanical & Electrochemical Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanical properties (storage modulus, E') by DMA • Electrochemical properties (Nyquist & bode plot) by EIS
Others	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conversion of the reaction by FT-IR • Lithium salts dissolution in the resin matrix by XRD

Results and Discussion

Thermal Analysis

• (DSC) Affected on the glass transition temperature (T_g) by different molecular structure in curing agents

Mechanical & Electrochemical Analysis

- (EIS) Increased number of ions in the matrix play an effective role to diffuse ions more than the lower concentration
- Investigated the matrix phase changes were affected on ionic movement by temperature changes

Others

Summary and Conclusions

- Investigated a profound impact on thermal stability, mechanical properties and electrochemical properties **by curing with different molecular structure of curing agents**
- Increased thermal stability by examining the trend in T_{d10} : (**aromatic** > **alicyclic** > **linear**)
- Found mechanical and electrochemical properties to be affected by the molecular structure of the curing agent used.
- Require to study further in terms of ion transport by polymer chain flexibility and electrochemical stability